

**Exploring University Professors' Perception of Continuous
Professional Training: Professors of English
at ESEFK as a Case Study**

By

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Abstract:

Owing to its immense significance in ensuring quality education and teacher professionalism, Continuous Professional Training (CPT) alerts many researchers nowadays. Governments and education ministries across the globe have deposited massive investments in CPT practices to advance the teaching-learning experience. Organizations such as OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) (2013) and the European Commission (2012) have compelled countries to provide constructive feedback and accountability procedures for in-service training (ITT) in the course of educators' employment. This paper shifts focus from pre-existing theories to research-based, updatable knowledge from the lenses of university professors in the region of Kenitra, Morocco. Hence, instructors' beliefs regarding continuous training prompted the current study. By incorporating evidence from a survey study on university professors of the Higher School of Education and Training of the English department and following the premises of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the study demonstrated that university professors develop a high tendency toward CPT regardless of the limitations related to the organization and planning of lifelong training. To ensure the accuracy of the findings, data was analyzed using the SPSS software.

Keywords: CPT, TPB, attitudes, perception.

Introduction

Many literary studies have addressed the value of professional training for educators, and its impact on teaching practices served as the foundation for this research project. With the rise of technology, around the 90s, old-fashioned approaches to teaching gradually diverged focus from teacher-centered methods to novel student and job-centered modes of learning. The 21st-century educational experiences emerged to mandate teacher training as life-long rather than once-in-a-lifetime training (Bouhaissa & Morchid, 2022). Past research has thus focused on CPT practices performed by academics and the factors influencing those practices (Agrati, 2021; OECD, 2013, OECD, 2018; Timperley et al., 2007). In essence, CPT ensures educators who are confident, ambitious, and self-conscious about developing their knowledge given the immense updates in the curriculum and the diversity of students to enhance their repertoire of teaching skills (Day, 1999).

In his article 'Closing the Gap on Effective Professional Development', Guskey (2009) asserted that the effectiveness of sustained and job-embedded professional training on instructional practices is closely related to improving student outcomes. Guskey urges leaders to be thoughtful and skilled consumers toward the available work in the field of their interest. By accessing globally validated sources of knowledge such as ERIC (Educational Resources Information Center), instructors can better enhance their CPT levels. Rigorous and credible evidence from CPT consultants is essentially required, and policymakers, at every level of education, should critically evaluate all forms of CPT, including setting goals for professional training activities and providing accurate evidence that is scientifically defensible (Guskey 2000, 2001).

Day (1999) advocated for the implementation of reflective practice partnerships for professional training. He emphasized three main areas to address reflection as a process for learning and change. The former area is bringing both the academia staff and schoolteachers together, regardless of their distinct roles, (Day, 1991; Cuban, 1992; Zeichner, 1995) by accepting the critical eye and intervention of others, including teachers, university tutors, schools and departments of education; they can work hand in hand to develop their practices as well as those of others. The second area is embracing the drawbacks resulting from teacher-peer or teacher-academician relationships to maintain long-term relationships. Consequently, teachers attain their potential by engaging in professional development through systematic investigation of practice. The latter area Day emphasized was maintaining professionalism by reflecting commitment, thoughtfulness, learning, experience, and energy (Devaney & Sykes, 1988, p. 20).

Nonetheless, educators' beliefs about the aspects of professional training differ from the data supporting those claims since not all educators receive the same level of training or have the same experiences in the classroom. Moreover, professional training approaches often lack focus, coherence, sufficient time and interaction, and practice opportunities for educators (Blank, de las Alas, & Smith, 2008, p. 3). In this vein, few studies have explored the university professors' perception in developing countries, particularly in Morocco, where educators feel torn between balancing learners' requirements, the demands of the educational field, and the prerequisites of the current and future endeavors (Bouhaissa & Morchid, 2022). To remedy the gap existing in this area of study, the purpose of this paper is to acknowledge the dynamics responsible for maintaining professional development practices from the lenses of university professors of Kenitra Higher School of Education and Training (ESEFK).

Significance of the Study

By conducting a context-dependent study in the Higher School of Education and Training in Kenitra, Morocco, new conclusions can be drawn and generalized to other similar regions with comparable characteristics. As educational contexts continue to evolve, conducting a case study in Morocco is crucial to examine how various factors shape the perception of teachers of professional development initiatives beyond the actual training and within a developing country setting.

Research Hypotheses

The literary database provides a rich context for the many hypotheses evolving around educators' different presumptions on continuous training. Therefore, this study evaluates the existing assumptions on how teachers perceive professional training through the backing of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991). This theory has been widely applied in the prediction and change of behavior by examining three types of beliefs: behavioral beliefs, normative beliefs and control beliefs. While behavioral beliefs reflect the individual's positive or negative evaluation of performing the behavior, normative beliefs are the individual's beliefs about whether significant others approve or disapprove of the behavior. Control beliefs, on the other end, are the individual's beliefs manifested in those factors that may facilitate or impede the execution of that particular behavior (Ajzen, 1991). The following research hypotheses are based on the constructs of the TPB theory:

- 1) Professors hold positive attitudes toward CPT.
- 2) The academic environment influences, by some means, how teachers perceive CPT.
- 3) Professors have access to resources by which they engage in lifelong professional training.

Research Background

In a survey conducted at Taif University English Language Centre in Saudi Arabia, positive feedback came from the respondents regarding their support for continuous learning and experiential learning falling under the umbrella of learner-centeredness. However, the participants were concerned about some areas of improvement regarding institutional policies and backing for the absence of experts' instructions. The participants critiqued the indigenization of activities in CPT practices as the one-week duration allocated to work on CPT practice does not allow them sufficient time to give feedback and coaching. Alongside this, follow-up activities were not highly paid attention to (Al Asmari, 2016).

In the same vein, the Department of Education at Qatar University conducted a qualitative study in which sixteen female English language teacher were interviewed to provide insights about their views on CPT. The findings revealed that participants had different experiences with CPT, yet, they reported a positive experience compared to those who were less committed to the profession (Floyd & Qadhi, 2021). The paper proposed a dynamic alternative to traditional continuous development models to ease their personal and professional discourse with other tutors.

As educational contexts continue to evolve, conducting a case study in Morocco is crucial to examine how various factors shape the perception of teachers of professional development initiatives within a developing country setting.

Methodology

Objective

This research inquiry intends to assess university professors' views about continuing professional training and examine, within a refined setting, the dynamics involved in favoring the adoption of CPT practices in the university environment. Beyond this, it seeks to identify potential areas for improvement in current professional training offerings for university faculty.

Philosophical Worldview

The thesis in the current inquiry is framed within the positivist worldview, as there is overt concern with quantifying teachers' perception of CPT. Searching through history, Positivism emerged in the 19th century as the dominant paradigm that uses scientific methods at all (Kaboub, 2008). However, the Post-positivist tradition is not an option for the study since the qualitative data is likely to destroy the essence of the inquiry for it critiques the absolute nature of truth (Letourneau & Allen, 2006). Thereby, the research stance is clear: only through a quantitative approach and survey design, the nature of the phenomenon is demonstrated. Such a scientific mechanism is more likely to yield reliable and valid results in this study, ensuring that the data collected can accurately measure teachers' perception of CPT.

Instrument of Data Collection

This inquiry uses quantitative methods to collect and analyze data relying on the Google Forms tool for survey construction and the SPSS software for data analysis (version 30.0.0.0 (172)). The participants in the study are 11 male and 9 female professors of English working at the Higher School of Education and Training (ESEFK), Morocco. Apart from the collection data methods, the extra information was derived from authentic websites mainly Google Scholar, ERIC and ResearchGate databases.

Population and Sampling

Estimating the current criteria including the time factor, the geographical factor, the accessibility factor, and the willingness to participate for the purpose of the study (Dörnyei, 2007), convenience sampling is well-suited to the premises of the research prompt. As such, twenty university professor from the English department at the Higher School of Education and Training have participated in the current study. The sampling parameter of the target population of this study consists of university professors and instructors of English—both male and female—who have taught different modules of English Studies and share a common interest in education. Whereas the sampling frame, as defined by Lohr (1999), includes the closest live persons in the researcher's perimeter.

Findings and Discussion

The main objective of this study is to investigate whether university professors of Kenitra Higher School of Education and Training (ESEFK) are in favor of CPT practices, whether they give or receive support from colleagues and administration, and whether they have the resources to advance in their CPT practices. In this vein, a survey was delivered to different university professors at ESEFK, males and females, and professors of the English department. The following table shows the demographics of the survey study respondents:

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Study's Participants

Parameter	Frequency	Percentage
Total	20	100%

Gender		
Male	11	55%
Female	9	45%
Age		
30 or younger	4	20%
31-40	6	30%
41 or above	10	50%
Years of Experience at the university level		
Less than 5	8	40%
5-10 years	9	45%
More than 10	3	15%

The table highlights the demographic characteristics of the population sample represented by 20 university professors from the Higher School of Education and Training in Kenitra. The study is variant in terms of females and males as the number of male respondents is 55% and 45% female respondents. Such percentage indicates a slight male predominance in this survey study. The age factor is significant as there is 10 individuals aging between 41 or above, in comparison to 4 professors aging between 30 or younger, and 6 individuals aging between 31 and 40 years old which mirrors wider trends in academia. At the experience level at university, the data clearly demonstrates a good number of experienced professors portrayed in 45% of professors with 5 to 10 years of university-level experience. Nevertheless, professors with above 10 years of experience represent low frequency represented by 3 out of 20 individuals.

Table 2: University Professors' responses to different items in the questionnaire

Items		Frequency	Percentage
I believe that continuous professional training is valuable for enhancing my teaching skills and effectiveness.	Disagree	0	0%
	Neutral	1	5%
	Agree	19	95%
I think participating in workshops, seminars, and webinars is necessary to grow professionally.	Disagree	0	0%
	Neutral	2	10%
	Agree	18	90%
I consider the time I invest in continuous professional training to be worthwhile and beneficial for my career.	Disagree	0	0%
	Neutral	2	10%
	Agree	18	90%
I feel that CPT content effectively addresses various skills and areas of language teaching and learning.	Disagree	0	0%
	Neutral	5	25%
	Agree	15	75%
I believe that CPT activities including language immersion programs enhance both communicative competence and cultural awareness of university professors.	Disagree	0	0%
	Neutral	4	20%
	Agree	16	80%
I believe that continuous professional training enhances my primary teaching responsibilities.	Disagree	1	5%
	Neutral	3	15%
	Agree	16	80%
I feel that professors' professional training programs prioritize quality over quantity.	Disagree	3	15%
	Neutral	6	30%
	Agree	11	55%

I believe that CPT activities are primarily designed to meet administrative requirements mainly accreditation standards, governmental regulations, and internal policies.	Disagree	5	25%
	Neutral	9	45%
	Agree	6	30%
The faculty has ongoing discussion groups on professional training issues.	Disagree	10	50%
	Neutral	8	40%
	Agree	2	10%
I feel that my department head usually consults me before designing any CPT activity.	Disagree	4	20%
	Neutral	13	65%
	Agree	3	15%
I value the opinions of my colleagues regarding continuous professional training and consider their experiences when evaluating its effectiveness.	Disagree	0	0%
	Neutral	6	30%
	Agree	14	70%
I often approach colleagues to provide me with professional help or guidance.	Disagree	0	0%
	Neutral	1	5%
	Agree	19	95%
I provide assistance to a colleague to help them solve a problem and/or improve their teaching practice.	Disagree	0	0%
	Neutral	2	10%
	Agree	18	90%
I feel supported by my colleagues in pursuing continuous professional training opportunities.	Disagree	1	5%
	Neutral	10	50%
	Agree	9	45%
I feel that there is a clear vision and strategy regarding the provision of CPT programs from CPT providers and policymakers.	Disagree	5	25%
	Neutral	12	60%
	Agree	3	15%
I feel my institution recognizes and values the continuous professional training I complete as part of my professional development.	Disagree	1	5%
	Neutral	12	60%
	Agree	7	35%
My institution provides sufficient financial support for me to engage in continuous professional training opportunities.	Disagree	7	35%
	Neutral	11	55%
	Agree	2	10%
I believe I have sufficient time in my schedule to participate in continuous professional training activities.	Disagree	6	30%
	Neutral	6	30%
	Agree	8	40%
I believe I have adequate time to reflect on and apply what I learn from continuous professional training to my teaching practice.	Disagree	2	10%
	Neutral	6	30%
	Agree	12	60%
I feel that continuous professional training is prioritized appropriately within my overall professional responsibilities.	Disagree	3	15%
	Neutral	10	50%
	Agree	7	35%
I feel that I have access to the necessary resources (e.g., materials, and technology) to effectively engage in continuous professional training.	Disagree	3	15%
	Neutral	6	30%
	Agree	11	55%

The three-point Likert scale was employed to facilitate and ease professors' responses and also ensure accurate results. To determine the rate of agreement of each statement, the mean scores need to be

calculated. By definition, the mean score is the sum of all values divided by the total number of values. Subsequently, the ranges of the scales are determined as follows:

- Disagree: 1.00 – 1.66
- Neutral: 1.67 – 2.33
- Agree: 2.34 – 3.00

1st Research Hypothesis: Professors hold positive attitudes toward CPT.

The first seven items of the survey aimed to verify whether professors at ESEFK approve of continuing professional training (CPT) alongside their professional teaching duties. Surprisingly, the professors' responses strongly supported and valued CPT. At a three-point Likert Scale, the mean score calculated by SPSS showed that the statements received the highest rate of agreement, varying respectively from 2,95; 2,90; 2,90; 2,75; 2,80; 2,75; 2,40. Ninety-five percent of respondents agreed, with eighty percent acknowledging that incorporating CPT into their teaching practices is beneficial and is mirrored through enhancing their primary teaching responsibilities. This reinforces the fact that they view CPT as valuable to their roles. Ninety percent of respondents also believe that investing time in CPT practices, including workshops, seminars and webinars, is indispensable for academic growth, while the remaining 10% believe that such activities do not add to professors' professional status. Overall, this consensus indicates that professors recognize the importance of adapting CPT activities to improve their pedagogical practices and effectiveness in the classroom environment. Similarly, fifteen out of twenty respondents strongly believe that CPT caters to different areas of teaching and learning. Furthermore, the sixth item demonstrated that eighty percent of professors consider that participating in language immersion programs develops communication proficiency and cultural awareness in the field of English teaching. However, despite this consensus, 55% of professors opposed to 15% acknowledge that not all CPT programs address qualitative purposes compared to the quantity of accumulated training.

2nd Research Hypothesis: The academic environment influences, by some means, how teachers perceive CPT.

The second seven items dictate interesting insights regarding the environmental support provided by colleagues and the administration. The mean score for the second part of the statements varies from 2,05; 1,60; 1,95; 2,70; 2,95; 2,90; 2,40. The first item received a neutral response as the highest rate of agreement, showcasing that there may be some recognition of administrative influence, yet, it is not perceived as the sole purpose of CPT. The second item has a rate of 1,60 which indicates a huge gap in terms of involving instructors in discussing and planning training activities. This lack of institutional engagement may suggest that CPT is not prioritized within the academic environment, potentially undermining its perceived value. As for the third item, the mean score is neutral but slightly leans toward disagreement with a percentage of 20%. In terms of peer-to-peer support, the majority of respondents (70%) strongly admitted that they rely on the opinions of other colleagues to evaluate their CPT practices. Moreover, 90% of the university professors assist others with their teaching responsibilities which shows their dedication towards collective professional training. However, a percentage of 45% receives guidance and support from colleagues about continuous training practices. The last item of the second collection suggests a moderate level of agreement. This suggests that also a collaborative academic culture may be lacking and surely influencing their perception of CPT.

3rd Research Hypothesis: Professors have access to resources by which they engage in lifelong professional training.

The data provided in the last seven items of the survey reveals interesting information about the factors enabling or prohibiting CPT occurrence with a mean score ranging between: 1,90; 2,30; 1,75; 2,10; 2,50; 2,20; 2,40. The first statement regarding the clarity of vision and strategy from CPT providers and policymakers received a mean score of 1,90, indicating a slight disagreement among respondents, suggesting a lack of a strategic direction for CPT programs. This fact also may suggest indifference

towards the continuous development completed by professors. The second statement receives a moderate mean score, with 35% admitting that the institution values the practices they participate in for their academic profile. The third statement, concerning financial support, received a low mean score of 1,75 reflecting significant concerns about inadequate institutional funding. On the other hand, respondents felt slightly more positive about their schedules, which highlights their availability for continuous development, though 30% feel constrained probably for being overwhelmed by the academic tasks assigned to them. Similarly, in the fifth statement, professors asserted that they have time to reflect on the previously conducted activities with a mean score of 2,50. Furthermore, the prioritization of CPT among other academic duties received a mean score of 2,20, indicating a neutral stance, with 35% of respondents admitting having a balanced schedule where CPT is well integrated into their timetable. Lastly, the access to necessary resources shows a positive mean score of 2,40, showcasing

This study, though not definitive, has unveiled insightful data in the Higher School of Education and Training (ESEFK). After analyzing the results obtained through the survey questionnaire, it is evident that the professors of English at ESEFK are optimistic in terms of continuing their academic development and hold positive attitudes toward their environment of academia staff. However, they may have differed in whether the practices they engaged in responded to their teaching goals and academic needs. Another backbone fact that the sample of twenty instructors revealed is the absence of guidance and support from the head responsible and administration. These findings proved the literature's insights highlighted by Guskey (2009), which include setting goals for professional training activities, conducting evaluation sessions, and ensuring access to a reliable and trustworthy training source provided by policymakers of CPT.

Conclusion

Attaining the esteemed level of professional training is still a long way to go in the Higher School of Education and Training in the region of Kenitra. This study has shown that the academia staff are motivated to pursue their professional training practices and that their environment is quite positive and supportive. However, the challenges arising from the inadequate support from their supervisors are a critical factor in enabling or disabling the effective professional development of university professors.

Research Limitations

The area of research on continuing professional training in professors' courses of employment is rich and diverse. However, I must acknowledge that I encountered certain constraints when conducting this paper. One notable challenge was the lower-than-expected number of participants in the survey. Additionally, the results of this paper are specific to professors of English teaching at ESEFK. Consequently, the results cannot be generalized to all university instructors at ESEFK. The low sample size may have also limited the generalizability of the study findings, as the representation of males and females is not proportionate. Still, the findings may be applicable to similar contexts with comparable characteristics of the population. Overall, further research is needed to validate and expand upon these findings to larger samples of the population; for instance, all instructors at ESEFK. I, thereby, commit to updating the results of this study at multiple stages, following the publication of the initial version.

Acknowledgments

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to Professor Nabil MORCHID for their invaluable guidance in selecting the research topic, their insightful feedback, and their generosity in dedicating time at multiple stages of this research. Additionally, I extend my gratitude to the professors who contributed to the data collection process, as their involvement was essential to the completion of this paper.

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